

Workshop Bedah JOPE Menuju DOAJ

Kamis, 23 Desember 2021

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EIC REGISTER JOURNAL, IAIN Salatiga
Associate Editor DOAJ

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Understanding DOAJ

Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) atau Direktori Jurnal Akses Terbuka adalah situs web yang mencantumkan daftar jurnal akses terbuka, dikelola oleh Infrastructure Services for Open Access (IS4OA). Proyek ini mendefinisikan jurnal akses terbuka sebagai jurnal ilmiah dan keilmuan yang memenuhi standar kualitas tinggi melalui penelaahan sejawat atau kontrol kualitas editorial serta "menggunakan model pendanaan **yang tidak mengenakan biaya kepada pembaca atau institusi mereka untuk mengaksesnya**".

BOAI definition of OPEN ACCESS

- ▶ Definisi oleh **Budapest Open Access Initiative** tentang "akses terbuka" digunakan untuk menentukan hak-hak yang diperlukan yang diberikan kepada para pengguna, untuk jurnal yang dimasukkan dalam DOAJ sebagai **hak untuk "membaca, mengunduh, menyalin, mendistribusikan, mencetak, mencari, atau menautkan ke naskah lengkap artikel-artikel tersebut"**. Tujuan DOAJ adalah untuk "meningkatkan visibilitas dan kemudahan penggunaan jurnal-ilmiah dan akademik akses terbuka sehingga meningkatkan penggunaan dan dampaknya".

History of DOAJ

- ▶ Open Society Institute mendanai berbagai proyek terkait akses terbuka setelah Budapest Open Access Initiative. Gagasan untuk DOAJ muncul dalam diskusi pada acara Nordic Conference on Scholarly Communication pada tahun 2002. Universitas Lund menjadi organisasi yang mengelola dan memelihara DOAJ. Pada Januari 2013, DOAJ kemudian diambil alih oleh Infrastructure Services for Open Access (IS4OA). IS4OA didirikan pada tahun 2012 di Inggris sebagai perusahaan amal nirlaba oleh advokat akses terbuka Caroline Sutton dan Alma Swan. Perusahaan ini yang mengelola DOAJ dan Open Citations Corpus.

DOAJ 2015 – 2021

- 2015, basis data DOAJ berisi daftar untuk 10.000 jurnal.
- 2012, Rata-rata empat jurnal ditambahkan setiap hari.
- 2016, DOAJ mengumumkan bahwa mereka telah menghapus sekitar 3.300 jurnal dari basis data mereka untuk memberikan keandalan yang lebih baik pada konten yang tercantum di dalamnya. Jurnal-jurnal yang dihapus tersebut dapat mengajukan permohonan Kembali.
- 2018, basis datanya berisi sekitar 11.210 jurnal.
- 2020, jumlah jurnal 15, 197. Indonesia No.1 sedunia.
- 2021, Jumlah jurnal 16, 545.

11 item/static page yang perlu disiapkan

- ▶ 1, Kontak Person
 - ▶ 2. P-ISSN dan E-ISSN
 - ▶ 3. Author Fees/ Payments (Langkahnya Journal Manager–Payments–Centang General Option–Centang Author Fees)/bikin static page
 - ▶ 4. Editorial Board/ Team
 - ▶ 5. Statement Policy Review/ Kebijakan Review (Doble Blind peer Review, Single peer Blind Review dan lain–lain)
-

- ▶ 6. Aims dan Scope Jurnal
 - ▶ 7. Author Guidelines
 - ▶ 8. Screening Plagiarism
 - ▶ 9. Statement Open access Jurnal
 - ▶ 10 Content Lisensi (<https://creativecommons.org/>)
 - ▶ 11. Statement Copyright and Permissions
-

Register Journal

REGISTER JOURNAL, 1979-8903 (PRINT)- 2503-040X (ONLINE) is OPEN ACCESS, Peer-reviewed, International ESCI Web of Science Indexed Journal which has the perspectives of languages and language teachings. This journal has the Focus and Scope at presenting and discussing some outstanding contemporary issues dealing with **Applied Linguistics and English Language teachings**.

This journal is published every June and December by **IAIN Salatiga**, Indonesia, and has been accredited by the Indonesian Ministry of Research, Technology and Higher Education (RistekDikti) of Republic of Indonesia in **SINTA (Achieving SINTA 2)** since 24th October 2018. The recognition is published in Director Decree (SK No. 30/E/KPT/2018) and it is effective until 2021. This journal has been successfully indexed IN **CLARIVATE ANALYTICS, Emerging Sources Citation Index (ESCI)** of **Web of Science** since June 2019.

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+ Subject

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10

per page

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*Stephanie Kullmann, Vera Valenta, Robert Wagner, C
Häring, Hubert Preissl, Andreas Fritsche, Martin Hen
Nature Communications. 2020;11(1):1-6 DOI 10.1038
[Abstract](#) | [Full Text](#)*

Tomás Eloy Martínez e as (des)memórias de Juan Do
(des)memories of Juan Domingo Perón

INDONESIA NO.1 DI DOAJ

— Country of Publisher

10

count ↑

Indonesia (1,720)

United Kingdom (1,664)

Brazil (1,549)

United States (821)

Spain (789)

Poland (648)

Iran, Islamic Republic of (564)

Russian Federation (430)

Turkey (430)

Italy (411)

⬆ Fulltext Language

1. INDONESIA 1,720

2. UK 1,664

3. BRAZIL 1,549

4. USA 821

5. SPAIN 789

- ▶ Dengan jumlah jurnal terbanyak di DOAJ merefleksikan Indonesia adalah
 - ▶ 1) **indeksasi yang sangat pas dengan konstelasi perjurnalan dan**
 - ▶ 2) **selaras dengan akreditasi jurnal nasional (ARJUNA)** yang menuntut best practice dalam pengelolaan tata Kelola jurnal dan kontennya dan juga
 - ▶ 3) menghindari praktik predatory journal.
-

- ▶ Berikut ini adalah 10 alasan penolakan/embargo DOAJ terhadap jurnal. 10 alasan ini adalah hasil pengamatan dan pengalaman mas Andista Candra Yusro, seorang Associate Editor DOAJ Indonesia yang mengunggah filenya di <https://zenodo.org/record/3899744#.Xyvl3jUxXIU>
- ▶ 1. Website jurnalnya mati/server down. jangan sampai terjadi.
- ▶ 2. Informasi yg berbeda-beda di websites misalnya masalah copyright di halaman copyright notice disebutkan copyright milik author tapi di metadata dan pdf artikel disebut copyright milik jurnal dan jika memang milik jurnal sebaiknya ada CTA/copyright transfer agreement. Juga di footer jurnal disebutkan misal lisensi CC BY tapi berbeda dengan di halaman abstrak yg lisensinya misal CC BY NC atau CC BY NC ND. harusnya lisensinya sama disemua halaman web.
- ▶ 3.terlambat terbit
- ▶ 4.jumlah editor minim.contoh setahun jurnal nerbitkan 12 artikel tapi editornya hanya 5.
- ▶ 5. Terlalu banyak editor dan reviewer yg jadi co-author dalam satu edisi terbitan.

- ▶ 6. Bahasa di websites gado-gado.misalnya English-Indonesian campur-campur dalam satu halaman dan di informasi websites secara umum.
 - ▶ 7.petunjuk penulisan di-upload di google drive, seharusnya di halaman web.
 - ▶ 8.editor jurnal terlalu lama merespon email editor DOAJ.
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- ▶ <https://www.jihadisjurnal.my.id/2021/07/contoh-copyright-milik-author-dan-milik.html>

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PENDAHULUAN

Contoh catatan REJECTION 1

Thank you for your application to list this title in DOAJ. Unfortunately, the application has not been successful as the journal does not currently meet our basic criteria for inclusion.

Specifically, the journal failed on the following points:

Endogeny. The proportion of published papers where at least one of the authors is an editor, editorial board member or reviewer, or affiliated to the journal's institution exceeds 20%, based on the research content of the latest two issues.

Peer review. Only 5 people are listed as peer reviewers, which is a rather small pool of reviewers. This raises concern regarding the robustness of the journal's review process.

Contoh catatan REJECTION 2

Specifically, the journal failed on the following points:

Endogeny. The proportion of published papers where at least one of the authors is an editor, editorial board member or reviewer, or affiliated to the journal's institution exceeds 20%, based on the research content of the latest two issues.

Unclear licensing information. The copyright notice mentions both CC BY and CC BY NC. Further the language used in the copyright and licensing notice is generally unclear in places.

Unclear fees information. The application indicates that an APC is charged, however the author guidelines state that no author fees are charged from submission and publication.

Contoh catatan REJECTION 3

- ▶ The journal does not employ good publishing practices. – The proportion of published papers where at least one of the authors is an editor, editorial board member or reviewer, or affiliated to the journal's institution exceeds 20%, based on **the research content of the latest two issues**.
- ▶ Additionally, **two editorial team members are also listed as peer reviewers**, which raises concern regarding the independence of peer review.
- ▶ Catatan: **Dilarang menjadikan editor sekaligus jadi reviewer**. Solusi: perkuat jaringan cyber silaturahmi antar editor berbagai kampus/ganti peran editor di masing-masing jurnal biar ada diversity.

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DOAJ operates an education and outreach program across the globe, focussing on improving the quality of applications submitted.

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This is a guest post by Sophy, our UX Designer. Accessibility has always been a top priority in doaj.org's redesign ... [More Read More...](#)

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REGISTER

7 langkah register jurnal ke DOAJ

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You are now logged in. When you submit your application, it will be registered to this account. Please note:

1. The application form takes approximately **30 minutes** to complete.
2. Your progress is automatically saved.
3. You can return to this application at any time by clicking *My account* → *Publisher* at the top.
4. You can print or download a PDF preview of the form.
5. You must apply online.

DOAJ only accepts fully open access journals

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APPLICATION PROGRESS

- 1** Open access compliance
- 2 About
- 3 Copyright & licensing
- 4 Editorial
- 5 Business model
- 6 Best practice
- 7 Review your answers

them for any other lawful purpose.

Does the journal adhere to DOAJ's definition of open access?

Yes

No

The journal website must display its open access statement. Where can we find this information?

Link to the journal's open access statement

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When did the journal start to publish all content using an open license?

2020

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Journal title

Jurnal Dinamika

Jurnal Dinamika

Alternative title (including translation of the title) (Optional)

Ma revue

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Does the journal embed and/or display licensing information in its articles?

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No

Recent article displaying or embedding a license in the full text

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Yes

No

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Editorial

Peer review

DOAJ only accepts peer-reviewed journals. Which type(s) of peer review does this journal use?

- Editorial review
- Peer review
- Blind peer review
- Double blind peer review
- Post-publication peer review
- Open peer review
- Other

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Link to the journal's **Instructions for Authors**

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Average number of **weeks** between article submission & publication

16

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\$ Business Model

Publication fees

Does the journal charge fees for publishing an article (APCs)?

Yes

No

Where can we find this information?

Link to the page where this is stated. The page must declare **whether or not** there is a fee to publish an article in the journal.

APPLICATION PROGRESS

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Best practice

The best practices in this section adhere to publishing standards based around findability, preserving the content and ethical publishing practices.

We encourage journals to adopt these best practices but they are **not** mandatory for DOAJ indexing.

Archiving policy

Long-term preservation service(s) where the journal is currently archived

- CINES
- CLOCKSS
- LOCKSS
- Internet Archive
- PKP PN
- PubMed Central (PMC)
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Does the journal allow for ORCID iDs to be present in article metadata? No

Does the journal comply with I4OC standards for open citations? Yes

I've reviewed the answers to my application and confirm that the information provided is accurate and true.

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